

ETHNOGRAPHIC TERMS IN LITERATURE: A CASE STUDY OF O'TKIR
HOSHIMOV AND MUHAMMAD YUSUF**Sattorova E'zoza Muzaffar qizi**Intern Teacher at Information Technology and Management University,
sattorovsezoz@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18604304>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek adabiyotida etnografik atamalarning o'rnini, xususan, O'tkir Hoshimov va Muhammad Yusuf ijodi misolida tahlil qilinadi. Etnografik atamalar moddiy va ma'naviy madaniyatni aks ettiruvchi lingvistik birliklar sifatida nafaqat buyum va urf-odatlar nomi, balki madaniy xotira va milliy identitet belgisi sifatida ham xizmat qiladi. Tavsifiy, kontekstual, qiyosiy va semantik tahlil asosida ushbu atamalarning badiiy matnlarni estetik, ramziy va madaniy ma'nolar bilan boyitishi yoritilgan. Hoshimov prozasida beshik, tandir, sandal va an'anaviy marosimlar kundalik hayot, ijtimoiy rasm-rusumlar va jamoaviy xotirani ifodalaydi. Yusuf she'riyatida esa tandir, osh, yor-yor, sunbul va yalpiz kabi atamalar mehmondo'stlik, jamoaviy birlik va qishloq turmush tarzini ramziy ifodalab beradi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, etnografik atamalar nafaqat lingvistik hodisa, balki milliy madaniy merosni asrab-avaylash va xalq dunyoqarashini aks ettirishda muhim badiiy vositadir.

Abstract: This article examines the role of ethnographic terms in Uzbek literature, focusing on the works of O'tkir Hoshimov and Muhammad Yusuf. Ethnographic terms, as linguistic units reflecting material and spiritual culture, serve not only as names of objects and traditions but also as markers of cultural memory and national identity. Through descriptive, contextual, comparative, and semantic analysis, the study highlights how these terms enrich literary texts with aesthetic, symbolic, and cultural meanings. In Hoshimov's prose, items such as beshik, tandir, sandal, and traditional ceremonies represent everyday life, social rituals, and collective memory. In Yusuf's poetry, terms like tandir, osh, yor-yor, sunbul, and yalpiz symbolize hospitality, communal unity, and rural lifestyle. The findings demonstrate that *ethnographic terms are not only linguistic phenomena but also important literary tools in preserving cultural heritage and reflecting the national worldview.*

Key words: *ethnographic terms; Uzbek literature; O'tkir Hoshimov; Muhammad Yusuf; national identity; cultural memory; symbolism; folk traditions.*

National literature serves as an effective expression of a people's cultural heritage, historical memory, traditions, and linguistic wealth. From this perspective, ethnographic terms (ethnographic terms, cultural realia) hold an important place in artistic literature. Ethnographisms are lexical units denoting concepts related to a nation's material and spiritual culture; they include names of clothing, food, household items, tools of labor, rituals, and traditions. Beyond merely being names of objects or indicators of reality, they also function in literary texts as elements of imagery, symbolism, and cultural identity. (Jalilova, 2023, p. 112).

In literary studies and linguistics, the following methods can be widely applied for the analysis of national vocabulary (including ethnographic vocabulary):

1. *Descriptive and typological analysis* – identifies ethnographic lexical units from the text of the work and classifies them into categories (for example, gastronomic, clothing, household, ritual);

2. *Contextual (context-based) analysis* – studies in which textual context ethnographic words or expressions are used, by whom, in relation to which event, and with what emotion. Through this analysis, the broader meaning of the word, its symbolic aspects, and figurative sense are revealed;

3. *Comparative (contrastive) approach* – compares national vocabulary with its equivalents in other languages, focusing on cases where certain words cannot be translated, identifying existing differences, gaps, and non-equivalent lexicon;

4. *Semantic and pragmatic analysis* – examines the primary meaning (denotation) and additional meanings (connotation) of ethnographic units. It also identifies their pragmatic role, that is, what function they perform in the text (for example, identification, emphasizing national identity).

In literature, the significance of ethnographisms is manifested in several aspects.

Firstly, ethnographisms play an important role in preserving cultural memory, since words expressing national values reach their readers through the text.

Secondly, they serve to strengthen national identity. The unique features of a nation’s identity are expressed through language and literature. These units, representing the name of the geographical area, embody the culture and geographical landscape of the people. Moreover, such words as *Samarqand noni*, *Buxoro ipak matosi*, *Xorazm lazgisi*, *Qo’qon do’ppisi* indicate not only the type of product, but also the specific values and habits of those regions (Sattorova, 2025, p.9).

Thirdly, they can also be studied as a means of linguo-cultural analysis, functioning as a bridge that connects language and culture. (Kamilov, 2023, p. 24).

Fourthly, ethnographisms are important in creating an artistic and aesthetic impact in the text. Ethnographisms such as a simple Uzbek *doppi* (skullcap) or *tandir* (clay oven) vividly bring the traditional atmosphere before the reader’s eyes. (Yakubova & Begmatova, 2025, p. 48).

In Uzbek literature, many examples of this phenomenon can be found. In particular, it is vividly reflected in the works of the People’s Writer of Uzbekistan O’tkir Hoshimov and Muhammad Yusuf. In O’tkir Hoshimov’s prose, elements of national spirit are conveyed through depictions of ordinary people’s daily life, traditional elements of the neighborhood environment, as well as values and customs. (Kamilov, 2023). For example, in the works “*Ikki eshik orasi*”, “*Dunyoning ishlari*”, “*Tushda kechgan umrlar*”, and “*Shamollar esaveradi*” the life of the people, their customs, and their religious-spiritual traditions and values are clearly expressed and appear as markers of national identity. In the novella “*Dunyoning ishlari*”, the traditional values of the Uzbek people are illuminated through details depicting the image of the mother, household items, rituals, and neighborhood life. In analyzing the novella, researchers particularly emphasize the mother’s patience, her devotion to family values, as well as the symbolic use of ordinary household objects (Normurodova, 2024).

The ethnographisms are used in the literary works of O’tkir Khoshimov can be presented in the following table as an example:

1-jadval

Name of the work	<i>Ethnographisms related to ceremonies and traditions</i>	<i>Food-related ethnographisms</i>	<i>Object/clothing ethnographisms</i>

Dunyoning ishlari	<i>beshtik, beshtik to'y, sunnat to'y, alla, aqiqa;</i>	<i>atala, moshkichiri, go'ja, sumalak;</i>	<i>gilam paypoq, chodirxayol;</i>
Ikki eshik orasi	<i>choyxorlik, kelin salom, yor-yor; sunnat to'y;</i>	<i>xo'rozqand, sumalak, mastava;</i>	<i>adras, do'ppi, qiyiqcha, qiyiq do'ppi; oftoba, sandal</i>
Tushda kechgan umrlar	<i>janoza, fotixa;</i>	<i>obi non, bo'g'irsoq, patir; chuchvara, go'ja, qaymoq, mastava, ayron;</i>	
Nur borki soya bor	<i>Navro'z, Sumalak, Mehrjon, qo'y so'yish, osh tarqatish;</i>	<i>Halim, osh, qovurdoq, o'rik qoqi; tabaqa;</i>	<i>to'n, chappon, bo'z ro'mol,</i>
Shamollar esaveradi	<i>lapar, chilla;</i>	<i>asal choy, makaron sho'rva, patir;</i>	<i>yaktak;</i>

In the works of O'tkir Hoshimov, some terms are highly colloquial, and therefore certain of them are somewhat specific and more difficult to understand. For this reason, we have considered it appropriate to present some of them together with their lexical meanings. For example,

- **chodirxayol** – a special tent prepared for the bride during the wedding ceremony (Hoshimov,1989);

- **Mehrjon** – an ancient holiday name, which later acquired a symbolic meaning in literature (Hoshimov, 1986);

- **sandal** – a traditional type of “stove” used for heating the house by placing embers inside (Hoshimov, 2016);

- **oftoba** – a household item used for washing hands (Hoshimov, 2016);

- **chilla** - the coldest forty days of winter, a traditional calendrical concept (Hoshimov, 2017);

- **go'ja** – a dish made by boiling rice and mixing it with yogurt (Hoshimov, 1977).

The People's Poet of Uzbekistan, Muhammad Yusuf, is one of the most prominent figures of Uzbek poetry, in whose works ethnographisms are the depictions of national culture and everyday folk life occupy a particularly important place. The poet transforms scenes of ordinary people, traditional elements of life, and local cultural realities into poetic imagery through his remarkable artistic mastery. This firmly links his poetic uniqueness to the national context. In Muhammad Yusuf's poems, a number of traditional foods, ceremonies, and household items are employed with symbolic meaning. Among the most notable is the *tandir*, which in the poetic text signifies not only a means of baking bread but also a valued symbol of home, community, and the everyday life of common people. For instance, his popular “*Parijning eng go'zal*

restoranlarini bitta tandiringga alishmasman men” (Muhammad Yusuf, 2007) this piece of the poem is a clear reflection for our viewpoint (Sattorova, 2025).

*Bir payola choy, bir kosa osh,
Shuni topolmaydi qanchalab yosh (M.Yusuf, 2007).*

Here, *osh* is not only a dish but also a symbol of folk hospitality and communal unity. In Uzbek tradition, *osh* is the main food prepared at weddings and community gatherings. Through the word *osh*, the poet evokes the people’s solidarity and harmony.

*Somon hidlarida tong otadi,
Bog’lam bog’lam umidlar bilan. (M. Yusuf, 2007).*

In this passage, *somon* is a term characteristic of the Uzbek mentality and agriculture, referring to the by-product left after harvesting. In livestock farming and household life, it serves as fodder for domestic animals. Moreover, it can also be used in house construction, particularly in mixing mud for building.

*Sunbul hidi kelar dalalardan,
Yalpiz qo’shib choy damlar onam. (M. Yusuf, 2007).*

In this poetic passage, the words *yalpiz* (mint) and *sunbul* (ear of grain) are regarded as ethnographisms: *sunbul* refers to grain spikes, while *yalpiz* is a plant traditionally used in folk medicine by adding it to tea. These ethnographisms serve to animate the national way of life and family values through poetic imagery.

In the works of O’tkir Hoshimov and Muhammad Yusuf, ethnographisms appear as an integral component of the national culture and the spirit of the people. Both in prose and poetry, they serve as a means of evoking a sense of national identity in the reader and vividly reflecting everyday folk life. For example, in the literary works of Hoshimov, *tandir, supa, dasturxon, qo’noq, qoqi, lagan, pichoqbozlik* are the type of ethnographisms which reflect neighborhood life, ceremonies, and traditions. In Muhammad Yusuf’s poems *tandir, ko’rpacha, do’ppi, qo’y so’yish, o’rikqoqi, lagan* are the words symbolically express the people’s way of life, hospitality, and values.

These ethnographisms are not merely ordinary language units; rather, through them, the people’s ancient worldview, everyday life, religious beliefs, and national values are vividly and expressively woven into the literary text. Moreover, they play an important role in preserving the national spirit in literature, sustaining cultural memory, and transmitting it to future generations.

As we see in the works of Hoshimov and Muhammad Yusuf, ethnographisms are not only a linguistic phenomenon but also an important reflection of the people’s spirit, national thinking, and literary heritage. Therefore, studying ethnographisms as a distinct layer in literary text analysis is one of the pressing scholarly tasks for Uzbek literary studies and linguoculturology.

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